

THE PLANNING, PREPARATION, AND DISPLAY OF THE ATLANTIS ORBITER

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The Space Shuttle Fleet

The Space Shuttle Fleet

1. **Enterprise** (used for landing tests - never flown in space: at the Intrepid Museum, NYC)
2. **Columbia** (first Shuttle, destroyed in 2003)
3. **Challenger** (Destroyed in 1986)
4. **Discovery** (retired on March 9, 2011; at the Smithsonian Institution)
5. **Atlantis** (retired July 21, 2011; at Kennedy Space Center Complex)
6. **Endeavour** (retired June 1, 2011; at the California Science Center in Los Angeles)

Orbiter Specifications

- ▶ Weight: (with three shuttle main engines)
176,413 pounds (80 tons)
- ▶ Length: 122.17 feet (37.2 m)
- ▶ Height: 56.58 feet (17.2 m)
- ▶ Wingspan: 78.06 feet (23.7 m)
- ▶ Maximum Payload: 55,250 lbs. (22,060 Kg)
- ▶ Max Payload at Landing: (Return Payload)
32,000 lbs. (14,400 Kg)

Structural Alloys Used in the Orbiter

- ▶ Aluminum Alloy 7075-T6
- ▶ Aluminum Alloy 2024-T81
- ▶ Magnesium Alloy HM21A-T8
- ▶ Titanium Alloy 6Al-4V
- ▶ Combination Aluminum and Titanium Alloys
- ▶ Combination Beryllium and Titanium Alloys

Paints and Coatings

- ▶ Dow Corning 3140 RTV Coating was used for the red, black, and blue.
- ▶ PPG Industries Koropon Epoxy Primer used on most of the aluminum components.
- ▶ C9 Ceramic Coating was used to harden the outer fabric of the surface insulation blankets (AFRSI)
- ▶ Dimethylethoxysilane (DMES) was used to waterproof surface insulation blankets (AFRSI)
- ▶ A vented white silicone elastomer coating was used to cover the Felt Reusable Surface Insulation (FRSI).

Thermal Protection System (TPS)

Reinforced Carbon-Carbon (RCC). Used primarily in the nose cap and the wing leading edges. Used where reentry temperature exceeded $1,260^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($2,300^{\circ}\text{F}$). Extremely expensive and delicate!!!!

High-Temperature Reusable Surface Insulation (HRSI) tiles. Used on the orbiter underside. Used where reentry temperature was below 1260°C .

Fibrous Refractory Composite Insulation (FRCI) tiles. Also used on the underside and some HRSI tiles were replaced by this type.

Flexible Insulation Blankets (FIB). Originally developed as AFRSI, a quilted, flexible blanket-like surface insulation. Used where reentry temperature was below 649°C ($1,200^{\circ}\text{F}$).

Felt Reusable Surface Insulation (FRSI). White Nomex felt blankets on the upper payload bay doors, portions of the mid-fuselage and aft fuselage sides, portions of the upper wing surface. Used where temperatures stayed below 371°C (700°F).

Gap Fillers (G/Fs). Either consisted of pillow/pad or Ames gap fillers. Consisted of Nextel alumina fabric and stuffed with alumina fiber and stitched with quartz thread (pillow/pad) or coated with black RTV or ceramic (Ames). Both G/F's were attached to the surface using Room Temperature Vulcanizing (RTV) adhesive. Used where temperatures do not exceed $1,200^{\circ}\text{F}$.

Thermal Protection System (TPS)

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- RCC
- HRSI Tile
- LRSI Tile
- AFRSI
- FRSI

High-Temperature Reusable Surface Insulation (HRSI) – Black Tiles

High-Temperature Reusable Surface Insulation (HRSI) – Black Tiles

Orbiter Showing Heat Resistant Tiles

Low-Temperature Reusable Surface Insulation (LRSI) – White Tiles

Flexible Insulation Blankets (FIB)

Felt Reusable Surface Insulation (FRSI)

Felt Reusable Surface Insulation (FRSI)

FRSI, FIB & LRSI on the Orbiter

Reinforced Carbon Carbon (RCC)

Scope of Work

- ▶ Thorough photographic documentation
- ▶ Complete conditions survey
- ▶ Archival research
- ▶ Translation of the operation and service manuals into a workable maintenance plan.
- ▶ Design and implementation of an environmental protection and monitoring plan to protect interior and exterior areas of the vehicle during the relocation, temporary storage, and construction of the exhibit building around the vehicle.
- ▶ Creation of a treatment and maintenance plan and training of the client's exhibit crew on how to properly maintain and monitor the artifact to ensure its long-term preservation.
- ▶ Creation of a periodic inspection schedule to allow the client to plan and budget for follow-up site visits by the conservation team.

Orbiter Processing Facility (OPF)

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Pre-Relocation – Assessment/Planning

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PRESERVATION PLAN
For the
ATLANTIS ORBITER
KENNEDY SPACE CENTER VISITOR COMPLEX
FLORIDA

Prepared for:
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Mail Code: DNPS
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Prepared by:
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Date: October 16, 2012

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**Kennedy
Space
Center**
VISITOR COMPLEX

KENNEDY SPACE CENTER VISITOR COMPLEX

KSCVC Artifact Collections Management Department

Space Shuttle *Atlantis*
OV-104
Initial Artifact Conservation/Preservation
Plan

DOC # ACM1201
Draft 6, October 9, 2012

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Conservation Treatment Philosophy

Initial cleaning, repairs, exhibition preparation and cyclical maintenance directive is to maintain the Orbiter in the decommissioned condition. This means that the Orbiter will retain marks, staining and damage related to its service history and final flight.

- ▶ Initial cleaning is intended to remove soiling accumulated since decommission, primarily handling and construction related deposits.
- ▶ Initial and subsequent repairs are intended to stabilize TPS materials and provide visual completeness wherever materials may be missing or removed.
- ▶ Cyclical Maintenance procedures are aimed at minimal intervention methods required to maintain the Orbiter dust free and address any minor fluid spills.

Observed Conditions to be Preserved

**Low-Temperature
Reusable Surface
Insulation (LRSI) – White
Tiles**

**As found condition of
the tiles showing wear
and new replacement
tiles.**

Observed Conditions to be Preserved

**High-Temperature
Reusable Surface
Insulation (HRSI) –
Black Tiles**

**As found condition
showing discoloration
of the tiles due to
thermal exposure and
new replacement tiles.**

Observed Conditions to be Preserved

Flexible Insulation Blankets (FIB)

As found condition showing repairs to the insulating blanket.

Atlantis Orbiter Being Transported to New Display Building

Atlantis Orbiter in New Display Building

Display Building with Orbiter Inside on Display Frame

Installation of Silica Gel Packs

Installation of Shrink-wrap

Installation of Shrink-wrap

Installation of Shrink-wrap

Conservation Treatments Performed

- ▶ Removal of Shrink Wrap
- ▶ Removal of Water Intrusion Tape, External Covers & Desiccant
- ▶ Cleaning
 - **Dry Cleaning** - Dust should be removed from exterior TPS surfaces using dry methods wherever feasible.
 - **Wet Cleaning** - Tenacious soiling and stains not related to the Orbiter's decommissioned condition required wet cleaning using an approved dilute surfactant or solvents and pads, cloths or sponges.
- ▶ Repairs
 - **RSI Tiles** - Clear Tetraethyl Orthosilicate (TEOS) was used for all flight damages to aid in preservation. No other repairs were performed to the tiles.

Training of Maintenance Staff

Hydraulic Fluid Drips from Swing Stage

Cleaning – Dry Dusting

Cleaning – Dry Dusting

Cleaning - Vacuuming

Cleaning - Vacuuming

Treatment Report and Maintenance Plan

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Updated: July 1, 2013.

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Final Display

Final Display

Final Display

Thank You

- ▶ Daniel Gruenbaum - Delaware North Companies Parks & Resorts
- ▶ Ray Propst, Vehicle Operations Chief, USA
- ▶ Louis Berios, NASA
- ▶ Patty Miller – 2 Arts Conservation
- ▶ Mark Rabinowitz – Conservation Solutions, Inc.